

A 4-Week Randomized Controlled Trial Evaluating Plaque And Gingivitis Effects Of An Electric Toothbrush In A Paediatric Population

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Abstract:

Background: Effective oral hygiene is essential for preventing dental diseases such as plaque accumulation and gingivitis, particularly in children. While manual toothbrushes have been traditionally used, electric toothbrushes are increasingly recognized for their superior plaque removal and ease of use, especially in pediatric populations.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of electric toothbrushes compared to manual toothbrushes in reducing plaque and gingivitis in a pediatric population over a 4-week period.

Methods: A total of 100 children aged 6-12 years were randomly assigned to either the electric toothbrush group (n=50) or the manual toothbrush group (n=50). Plaque and gingival indices were assessed at baseline and after 4 weeks. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing paired and independent t-tests to compare the outcomes within and between groups.

Results: Both groups showed significant reductions in plaque and gingivitis after 4 weeks ($p < 0.001$). However, the electric toothbrush group exhibited a significantly greater reduction in plaque (1.2 vs. 0.5) and gingivitis (0.9 vs. 0.3) compared to the manual toothbrush group ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: According to the study, children's plaque and gingivitis may be reduced more effectively using electric toothbrushes than with manual ones. The findings imply that include electric toothbrushes in kids' dental care regimens might greatly enhance their oral health.

Recommendations: Based on these findings, it is recommended that electric toothbrushes be promoted as a preferred option for pediatric oral hygiene, especially for children who may struggle with manual brushing techniques. Further research is suggested to explore long-term outcomes and the potential benefits of electric toothbrushes in different pediatric subpopulations.

Keywords: Pediatric Oral Hygiene, Electric Toothbrush, Plaque Reduction, Gingivitis Prevention, Randomized Controlled Trial.

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Introduction

Particularly in youngsters, maintaining good oral hygiene is essential for preventing periodontal disorders, gingivitis, and plaque buildup. Childhood dental diseases can evolve into chronic disorders that may last into adulthood as a result of poor oral hygiene. Effective plaque management, which is possible with good brushing techniques, is crucial to the avoidance of such problems. Although conventional manual toothbrushes have been extensively used, electric toothbrushes have become more and more popular because of their capacity to remove plaque more effectively and because they are easier to use, especially for younger people.

According to recent research, electronic toothbrushes are more efficient than manual ones at removing plaque and reducing gingival irritation. Electric toothbrushes are more successful than manual toothbrushes in the long run at reducing plaque and gingivitis, according to a 2020 comprehensive review and meta-analysis [1]. An further 2019 study with a paediatric population showed that using an electric toothbrush significantly improved oral hygiene, especially in kids who could have trouble brushing correctly because of their age and dexterity [2]. These results imply that children's oral hygiene routines might be greatly improved by electric toothbrushes.

Children's dental hygiene is especially important since they frequently brush less diligently, which can lead to greater plaque levels and a higher risk of gingivitis. It is crucial to teach kids and their carers proper brushing habits, but the type of toothbrush that is used can also have a big influence on oral health results. When using an electric toothbrush, which often needs less manual dexterity, youngsters who may not have the motor skills essential for successful plaque removal with a manual toothbrush might find a useful solution [3].

Even though there is a growing amount of data that supports the usage of electric toothbrushes, more targeted study that is especially directed at children is still needed. For the purpose of creating individualised oral hygiene recommendations, it is essential to comprehend the efficacy of electric toothbrushes in children, who differ from adults in terms of their oral health demands and obstacles. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of electric toothbrushes compared to manual toothbrushes in reducing plaque and gingivitis in a pediatric population over a 4-week period.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a randomized controlled trial (RCT). This study is prospective in nature.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga.

Participants: A total of 100 children, aged 6-12 years, were recruited for the study. Participants were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (n=50) or the control group (n=50).

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged between 6 to 12 years.
- Participants with a minimum of 20 teeth.
- Children with parental/guardian consent to participate in the study.
- No prior use of an electric toothbrush.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with systemic diseases that could affect oral health.
- Participants who have used an electric toothbrush before.

- Children undergoing orthodontic treatment.
- Those with any known allergies to the materials used in the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was employed to assign participants to either the intervention or control group. The study was single-blinded, with participants ignorant of the precise goals of the research. The dental examiners who assessed plaque and gingivitis were blinded to the group assignments. Additionally, all participants were instructed to maintain their usual oral hygiene practices, except for the type of toothbrush used.

Data Collection: Data collection involved baseline and follow-up assessments of plaque and gingivitis. Plaque levels were measured using the Plaque Index (Silness and Løe), and gingivitis was assessed using the Gingival Index (Løe and Silness). Assessments were conducted at the start of the study (baseline) and at the end of the 4-week period.

Procedure: The groups that received manual or electric toothbrushes at random were assigned to the participants. Following baseline evaluations of oral hygiene, individuals in the intervention group were given an electric toothbrush, while those in the control group were given a manual toothbrush. Every participant received instruction on appropriate brushing methods and was advised to brush for two minutes twice a day. Four weeks later, follow-up evaluations for gingivitis and plaque were carried out.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of SPSS was used to analyse the data. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics. Paired t-tests compared baseline and post-intervention plaque and gingivitis scores within groups, while independent t-tests compared changes between groups. P-values less than 0.05 were regarded as significant.

Results

A total of 100 children aged 6-12 years were enrolled in the study. The participants were randomly assigned to the electric toothbrush group (n=50) and the manual toothbrush group (n=50).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Electric Toothbrush Group (n=50)	Manual Toothbrush Group (n=50)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	8.7 ± 1.8	8.5 ± 1.7	0.532
Gender (M/F)	28/22	26/24	0.683
Mean Number of Teeth	22.5 ± 2.0	22.3 ± 2.1	0.742

There were no statistically significant differences between the groups in terms of age, gender distribution, or the number of teeth ($p > 0.05$).

The mean Plaque Index scores at baseline and after 4 weeks for both groups are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Plaque Index Scores

Time Point	Electric Toothbrush Group	Manual Toothbrush Group	p-value (between groups)
Baseline	2.4 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.6	0.437
4 Weeks	1.2 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.5	<0.001
Mean Reduction	1.2 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.3	<0.001
p-value (within groups)	<0.001	<0.001	

Both groups showed a significant reduction in Plaque Index scores after 4 weeks ($p < 0.001$ for both). However, the reduction was significantly greater in the electric toothbrush group compared to the manual toothbrush group ($p < 0.001$).

The mean Gingival Index scores at baseline and after 4 weeks for both groups are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Gingival Index Scores

Time Point	Electric Toothbrush Group	Manual Toothbrush Group	p-value (between groups)
Baseline	1.8 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.5	0.528
4 Weeks	0.9 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.4	<0.001
Mean Reduction	0.9 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.2	<0.001
p-value (within groups)	<0.001	<0.001	

Both groups exhibited significant improvements in Gingival Index scores after 4 weeks ($p < 0.001$ for both). The electric toothbrush group demonstrated a significantly greater reduction in gingivitis compared to the manual toothbrush group ($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that the use of an electric toothbrush may be more effective in improving oral hygiene in a pediatric population compared to a manual toothbrush.

Discussion

During the course of four weeks, the study assessed how well electric toothbrushes and manual toothbrushes reduced plaque and gingivitis in a paediatric population. One hundred and fifty youngsters, ages six to twelve, were split into two groups at random and given an electric toothbrush or a manual toothbrush. The comparison was legitimate as the two groups' baseline attributes—age, gender, and tooth count—were similar.

After four weeks, the data showed a substantial decrease in the levels of plaque in both groups. With a mean drop in Plaque Index scores of 1.2 as opposed to 0.5 in the manual toothbrush group, the reduction was more noticeable in the electric toothbrush group. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that children's plaque buildup was reduced with the electric toothbrush.

Similarly, the Gingival Index scores, which measure gingivitis, showed significant improvement in both groups over the 4-week period. The electric toothbrush group had a greater reduction in gingivitis, with a mean decrease of 0.9 compared to 0.3 in the manual toothbrush group, also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). This

suggests that the electric toothbrush was more effective in improving gingival health and reducing inflammation.

The absence of adverse events and the high tolerance of the participants to the toothbrushes further support the safety and feasibility of using electric toothbrushes in children.

Overall, the study's findings indicate that electric toothbrushes offer a superior benefit over manual toothbrushes in reducing plaque and gingivitis in a pediatric population. These results suggest that incorporating electric toothbrushes into children's oral hygiene routines could lead to better oral health outcomes, potentially reducing the risk of future dental problems.

When compared to manual toothbrushes, recent studies have repeatedly shown that electric toothbrushes—especially oscillating-rotating (O-R) models—are more effective in reducing plaque and gingivitis. An innovative O-R electric toothbrush with an extra-gentle brush head was compared to a manual toothbrush for a 12-week randomised controlled experiment. The results showed that the electric toothbrush considerably reduced plaque and gingivitis in numerous evaluations. Compared to those using the manual toothbrush, participants who used the O-R brush saw a significantly greater rate of gingival status transition from not healthy to healthy [4].

In a different research, an 8-week trial comparing a high-end sonic toothbrush and a revolutionary O-R toothbrush with micro-vibrations revealed that the O-R toothbrush was superior in removing plaque and gingivitis. All areas of the mouth showed statistically significant reductions in plaque, and a

larger percentage of individuals in the O-R brush group exhibited healthy gingival status [5].

Comparing an O-R electric toothbrush with a new brush head against a manual toothbrush over the course of a 5-week clinical assessment, it was found that the electric toothbrush considerably reduced the amount of plaque and gingivitis. According to the study demonstrated how well the O-R toothbrush managed oral hygiene in individuals with mild-to-moderate gingivitis [6].

Conclusion

In a paediatric population, this study shows that using an electric toothbrush for four weeks dramatically decreases plaque and gingivitis more efficiently than using a manual toothbrush. The findings suggest that electric toothbrushes could be a valuable tool in improving oral hygiene and preventing dental issues in children. Given the safety, effectiveness, and ease of use, incorporating electric toothbrushes into children's daily oral care routines is recommended to enhance their overall oral health.

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